

D6.2. DMP - Data Management Plan

WP	6	Project management
----	---	--------------------

Dissemination Level ¹	PU	Delivery date	12/04/2021
----------------------------------	----	---------------	------------

Lead beneficiary	UdG
Contributing beneficiaries	UC3M, COMPOXI

Topic manager approval	Name, date and signature
------------------------	--------------------------

Grant agreement 886519

ITD/IADP/TA AIR ITD

Project Acronym BEDYN

Project Title *Development of a methodology (test, measurement, analysis) to characterize the BEhaviour of composite structures under DYNamic loading*

¹Dissemination Level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

LIST OF VERSIONS

Version	Issue date	Changes	Author (affiliation)	Reviewer (affiliation)
01	12/04/2021	Initial outline	Emilio V. Gonzalez (UdG)	José Alfonso Artero (UC3M) Marc Gascons (COMPOXI) Vincent Jacques (DA)

LIST OF ASSOCIATED DOCUMENTS

Name	Type	Author (affiliation)

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 886519. This publication reflects only the author’s views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 886519

ABBREVIATIONS

DA	Dassault Aviation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
ITD	Integrated Technology Demonstrators
JU	Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking
MR	Member Repository
ORE	Open Research Europe (open access publishing platform)
PDC	Project Data Contact
TM	Topic Manager
TMR	Topic Manager Repository
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
UdG	Universitat de Girona
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document, D6.2. DMP - Data Management Plan, is a deliverable of the BEDYN project launched under the ITD, funded by the European Union's H2020 through Clean Sky 2 Programme under the Grant Agreement 886519.

The aim of BEDYN project is to address a methodology to properly characterize the dynamic behaviour up to rupture of thermoset polymer-based composite structures submitted to dynamic loading. Different main objectives can be identified:

- Ob. 1) Define a modelling approach for dynamic loading events, suited to industrial needs for emergency situations applications.
- Ob. 2) Define dynamic tests, which include the definition of: specimens, test setups, and data reduction methods. Three different specimen levels are set: "coupon", for characterizing basic properties of the composite material (ply), interlaminar (delamination) and adhesive interfaces; "element", they include what can be understood as small size demonstrator (under this category the response of the flexural, notch effects and bearing will be analysed); "structure", they are devoted for characterizing the behaviour at a subcomponent level under out-of-plane dynamic loads. In order to describe properly the possible dynamic effect in some material/structure behaviours, a quasi-static test campaign is also considered for any of the specimen levels accounted for.
- Ob. 3) Define a calibration and validation process of the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) models.
- Ob. 4) Demonstrate and evaluate the proposed methodology based on tests performed.

The BEDYN project will contribute towards the consolidation of the use of numerical simulation in the design phase of polymer-based composite structures under dynamic loading. The BEDYN project will address innovative technologies, allowing better product development thanks to an increased knowledge of the behaviour of composite materials under dynamic loading. Maturing and validation of technologies is a key aspect of integrating research in the development process of industrial activities and next generation aircrafts.

The expected type of research data that will be generated along the progress of BEDYN project will fall into the following two main categories:

- a. Definition of specimens, test setups, and data reduction methods for dynamic characterization under different loading conditions.
- b. Development of Finite Element Analysis (FEA) models, including constitutive models and modelling strategies aligned with industrial purposes.

The research data that compromise the commercialisation prospects or confidentiality terms will not be made available with others, and will be preserved under closed access terms within the members of the consortium and the Topic Manager (TM) in a designated private shared repository. Nevertheless, during and after the course of the project, if any data is intended to be shared with others typically via international scientific publications, it will be decided and agreed upon between the consortium members and the TM. It is worth mentioning that the research data to be shared with others will be deposited in an open access repository.

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. DATA MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSIBILITY	6
1.1. DMP Internal Consortium Policy.....	6
1.2. Data Management Responsible.....	6
1.3. Data nature, link with previous data and potential users	7
1.4. Data Summary.....	7
2. FAIR Data	9
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	9
2.2. Making data openly accessible	11
2.2.1. Confidential data.....	11
2.2.2. Open data.....	11
2.3. Making data interoperable	12
2.4. Increased data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	13
3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	13
4. DATA SECURITY	13
5. ETHICAL ASPECTS	13
6. OTHER ISSUES	13
ANNEX 1	14

1. DATA MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSIBILITY

1.1. DMP Internal Consortium Policy

The responsibilities associated to the Data Management Plan (DMP) will be managed by a specific person per each consortium partner, and the overall responsibility of the data management will be managed by the lead beneficiary of the project. The BEDYN project coordinator, Universitat de Girona (UdG), will be responsible for adopting and procuring a strategy for data maintenance, selecting a repository for data handling, uploading the data and ensuring that data is kept up to date. The project coordinator will also be responsible entity for all the relations and communications with the Topic Manager (TM). The different members of the consortium and the responsible contact for each partner are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Members of BEDYN consortium and TM, and responsible contacts.

Organization	Role	Responsible Contact
UNIVERSITAT DE GIRONA (UdG) PLAÇA SANT DOMENEC 3, GIRONA, SPAIN 17004	Lead beneficiary (Coordinator)	Project Coordinator: Dr. Emilio V. Gonzalez emilio.gonzalez@udg.edu
UNIVERSIDAD CARLOS III DE MADRID (UC3M) CALLE MADRID 126, GETAFE (MADRID), SPAIN 28903	Beneficiary	Contact: Dr. José Alfonso Artero-Guerrero jartero@ing.uc3m.es
COMPOXI S.L. (COMPOXI) CALLE PIC DE PEGUERA 15, GIRONA, SPAIN 17003	Beneficiary	Contact: Dr. Marc Gascons m.gascons@compxi.com
DASSAULT AVIATION (DA) AIRFRAME ENGINEERING	Topic Manager (TM)	Contacts: Vincent Jacques vincent.jacques@dassault-aviation.com Elisabeth De Blanpre elisabeth.De-Blanpre@dassault-aviation.com

1.2. Data Management Responsible

The Project Data Contact (PDC) will be responsible and in charge of the data management, uploading, maintenance, and updating. The details of the PDC are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Project Data Contact responsible.

Project Data Contact (PDC)	Dr. Emilio V. Gonzalez
PDC Affiliation	Universitat de Girona (UdG)
PDC e-mail	emilio.gonzalez@udg.edu
PDC telephone number	(+34) 682 81 24 50

Since the main data repository used in BEDYN project belongs to TM, support and assistance by the TM responsible listed at Table 1 will be ensured.

1.3. Data nature, link with previous data and potential users

BEDYN project involves manufacturing and experimental testing of specimens at three different levels of complexity and size (coupon, element, and structure), made with a selected thermoset composite material and an adhesive, as well as the development of numerical Finite Element Analysis (FEA) methods where well-suited constitutive damage models are formulated and implemented for the simulation of events under dynamic loading. Hence, the development of the BEDYN project will lead basically to the generation of experimental raw data (text files, spreadsheets, images and videos) and numerical simulation models (scripts and FEA data).

The generated experimental data will be used for understanding the material/structure under dynamic loading and for the development of reliable FEA models able to predict the response of the material. The data generated will be shared and used by the consortium partners, as well as by the TM, to progress on achieving the BEDYN objectives. International scientific publications and conference proceedings, strictly following the agreement and the dissemination terms mentioned by the TM, will be utilized by the scientific community and industries to further extend the knowledge on the topic and to speed up the innovation.

Each member of the consortium has its own previous non-published data/methods which can be used as reference for some developments in BEDYN and this information belongs to each member, and thus the member can decide to share or not, e.g. calculation sheets for data reduction. BEDYN project will use the data available within the consortium members and TM, such as in-house tools or software's, and from standards or published scientific data in view of defining the experimental procedures, generating the state-of-the-art review, etc.

The Access Rights to the different source data generated is defined in "Section 9: Access Rights" of the Implementation Agreement.

1.4. Data Summary

The global objective of the BEDYN project is divided into sub-objectives. They are identified and carried out through the development of the Work Packages (WP) summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. WPs of BEDYN project (for more information, see GA).

WP#	Title	Leader
WP1	Dynamic modelling of material and structure	UdG
WP2	Test coupons/elements/structures design	UdG
WP3	Test setup design	UC3M
WP4	Manufacturing: coupons, elements, structures and test rigs	COMPOXI
WP5	Quasi-static and dynamic tests	UC3M
WP6	Project management	UdG
WP7	Dissemination and Communication	UdG

The purpose of data generation is to accomplish the sub-objectives of the BEDYN project, and the collected data from a particular WP is used to feed as input to another WP as shown in Table 4. It is worth mentioning that the TM data inputs are implicitly included at any WP of the project. The TM data inputs are indispensable for the suitable development of the project, and they may include information of TM's needs, documentation of material/manufacturing, purchase of the material, knowledge, etc.

Table 4. Technical WPs: input and output data. TM inputs are implicitly included at any WP of the project.

Work Package	Lead beneficiary	Input data	Output data
WP1	UdG	TM specifications/needs; WP5	FE constitutive models Validation and Calibration of FE models Tools for dynamic test definition/analysis
WP2	UdG	TM specifications/needs; WP1; WP3	Definition of specimens
WP3	UC3M	TM specifications/needs; WP1; WP2	Definition of test setups
WP4	COMPOXI	TM specifications/needs; WP2; WP3	Manufactured plates data Plate cut data Non-destructive inspection data Manufactured test rigs
WP5	UC3M	TM specifications/needs; WP1; WP2; WP3	Experimental results raw data Data reduction methods

The project will generate data of various natures and Table 5 presents a global summary of the data generated, type of files and their formats, and the WP in which they are generated. In detail, the description of the data generated for each WP is provided in ANNEX 1.

Table 5. Summary of the nature of data generated.

Nature of data	Type of file	Standards	WP#
Report	Text	.docx; .pdf	All
FEA	Text Abaqus files Scripts	.txt; .docx; .pdf .inp; .odb .f (Fortran); .py (Python); .m (Matlab)	WP1
List of specimens, tests, instrumentation, planning and other info	Spreadsheet	.xlsx; .m (Matlab)	WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5

Test rigs	Cad files	.dwg	WP4
Specimen manufacturing data	Text	.docx; .pdf	WP4
	Cad files	.dwg; .sldprt (SolidWorks)	
Experimental raw results data and comparisons	Text	.txt; .docx; .pdf	WP1; WP5
	Images	.jpeg; .tif; .png	
	Video files	.MP4	
	Spreadsheet	.xlsx; .csv	

The bulk data generated during BEDYN project will be from the experimental tests campaign results and FEA data coded scripts (pre-process and post-process). The expected size of the data is estimated to be around 5 TB.

2. FAIR Data

Following the guidelines on the data management on Horizon 2020, BEDYN project partners will ensure that the research data generated is: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Three types of repositories are used in BEDYN project for sharing the information: among the TM and the consortium members; among the BEDYN's organizations and others (open access); and internal repositories of each member. They are briefly described in Table 6.

Table 6. Repositories used in BEDYN.

Repository	Nature	Observations
TM's Repository (TMR)	Private On-line share point	Findable, accessible and interoperable, at least by each responsible member listed in Table 1 The access permission is controlled safely by the TM Access management and maintenance is carried out by the TM
"Zenodo" https://zenodo.org/	Open science repository tool On-line share point	European Commission co-funded multi-disciplinary repository for data A "Community", named "BEDYN" associated to the project has been created for sharing all the public data. The community is managed by the PDC
Member Repository (MR)	Private	Each organization member will store and share the data generated by the personnel involved by each organization for the project, using their own internal repositories

All the partners agree on specific issues regarding metadata. They are:

- Deliverables
 - The deliverables are the reference project documents where the work developed is collected and explained in detail for each WP. For each deliverable, additional documents/datasets can be generated, and they will be collected in a table at the beginning of the corresponding deliverable as a guide of references for the reader.
 - The following naming convention for deliverables will be followed by all the partners (in blue are the fields to be specified for each deliverable):

BEDYN_DDeliverableNumber_DeliverableName_ResponsiblePartnerAcronym_vVersionNumber_Date(yymmdd)

It is worth mentioning that the Work Package Number is explicitly included as the first number that identifies the deliverable: each deliverable has two numbers, the first refers to the WP number, and the second, to the deliverable number associated to the referred WP. As an example, the present Data Management Plan deliverable is named as:

BEDYN_D62_DMPDataManagementPlan_UdG_v1_210412.pdf

- Control of versions. Each deliverable must include a table of versions with the following fields: Version, Issue date, Changes, Author (affiliation) and Reviewer (affiliation). Recall that a new version of a document requires a new signature of the TM, steering committee or WP leaders.
- The data is organised or formatted in a way that everyone working on it, now and in the future, knows the origin of the data. Accordingly, adequate metadata for each dataset to ease the interpretation of the data is provided:
 - Project funding information: “Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking”, “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”.
 - The name of the action “AIR ITD”, acronym “BEDYN” and grant number “886519”.
 - The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable.
 - Information about data collection (source, frequency and adjustments).
 - Keywords (keywords or phrases describing the subject or content of the data).
 - File formats.
 - Comments.

The datasets identified for the BEDYN project from each WP are enclosed in ANNEX 1.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Data availability is categorised in one of the three ways described below:

- “Confidential data”: accessible to all BEDYN partners (consortium and TM), retained within the partners and subject to the project Grant Agreement.
- “Open data”: shared for re-use or that underpins a scientific publication. These data will be shared via an open access research repository Zenodo or others, such as ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net/>).
- “Private data”: maintained by an individual partner for their own purposes.

As it can be identified, each category of data availability is linked to the data repositories listed in Table 6.

As it can be seen in ANNEX 1, data generated from the WPs 1 to 5 are defined under the “Confidential data” availability, and hence, it will be available only within the consortium members and the TM. Nevertheless, during the course of the project, if any data is intended to be shared to others, it will be decided and agreed upon between the consortium members and the TM. Scientific dissemination is deeply motivated in the BEDYN project, where two linked PhD theses are being developed, and therefore, some research data generated will be somehow published via scientific publications. On the other hand, data related to the WPs 6 and 7 that deal with data management and dissemination plan will be openly available (i.e. deliverables D6.2, D7.1 and D7.2).

2.2.1. Confidential data

All the data generated for each WP will be shared in TMR on-line repository platform (see Table 6). Accordingly, the project folders created in TMR will be structured following the BEDYN WPs summarized in Table 3. Other additional folders will be created for a better access to different information (for example, the folder for saving the Meeting Minutes of the bi-weekly meetings). All partners have external access, at least for each of the responsible listed in Table 1 to the TMR, with a username and password.

The details of the data generated that will be saved and shared in TMR is described in ANNEX 1.

2.2.2. Open data

The data that has to be made public will be shared through “Zenodo” multi-disciplinary repository under open license terms (see Table 6). All the public data generated will be in widely accepted standard formats and hence no specific tools or software is needed.

For sharing the BEDYN data in Zenodo, a “Community” named “BEDYN” has been created. The community is URL accessible by: <https://zenodo.org/communities/bedyn/>. The main details related to this openly accessible repository are described at following:

- Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon 2020.
- The DMR is the responsible for the community curation (see Table 2).

- Each data shared in Zenodo is assigned with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) that allows to identify and locate the data very easily. Even, all the data stored in Zenodo will use DOI versioning and this allows to update a dataset even after publishing. Zenodo handles the updated version numbers of these datasets.
- All BEDYN results/dataset deposited in Zenodo repository will provide search keywords along with metadata. Relevant metadata helps to facilitate the open access to data within the project members and to maintain organized data sets. Zenodo repository provides the following deposition metadata fields: title of data, description, files, type of upload, publication date, licence, DOI, keywords, relatable identifiers, etc. Metadata for each record is indexed and can be searched directly in Zenodo's search engine after publishing.
- Data in Zenodo can also be stored with an "embargo" period, where the data will be restricted until the end of the embargo period and will be public after this period.
- Appropriate data links can be sent to other members to access the files, and different levels of restricted access are offered in Zenodo (accordingly, "Confidential data" can also be managed in Zenodo repository; however, the TM preference is to use TMR for this data category).

Each partner will consider for publication their own experimental methods, either via a peer-reviewed publication, conference proceedings or by any other dissemination channel, but strictly following the dissemination terms and agreement by the TM. These dissemination documents will be uploaded in Zenodo (and others, such as ResearchGate). The data will be mainly extracted from the following deliverables (see ANNEX 1): BEDYN_D13, BEDYN_D14, BEDYN_D21, BEDYN_D22, BEDYN_D31, BEDYN_D32, BEDYN_D51 and BEDYN_D53.

The recently accessible open access publishing platform, launched by the European Commission as "Open Research Europe" (ORE), will be considered for publishing scientific articles based on data generated in BEDYN project. This platform is thought for publishing results of research funded by Horizon 2020 (and soon "Horizon Europe"). This platform offers a quick publication and peer review open to the research performed. Research articles, methods and essays can be submitted. The research must be original, not published on any other platform, and related to a project awarded in the Horizon 2020 program. Publication in the ORE is optional, free and meets the Open Access requirements of the H2020 programs. The article guidelines can be found at the following link: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines/>. Publishing in ORE or related common international journals will be agreed by the BEDYN consortium and the TM.

2.3. Making data interoperable

The data produced in the BEDYN project is interoperable between the different consortium members and the TM. As explained before, the output of some WPs from a partner is used as an input to another WP by another partner (see Table 4). Most of the data produced during the project will be of standard widely accepted formats (see Table 5 and ANNEX 1), such as Pdf files, Microsoft word files, Microsoft excel sheets, etc.

2.4. Increased data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Any re-use situations, during and after the project, must be communicated and agreed among the consortium members and the TM. The re-use of the data generated during and after the project will be focused on developing peer-reviewed scientific publications and other dissemination activities.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

At the moment, there is no immediate cost estimated for making the data FAIR. Zenodo repository is open-source and completely free and, for BEDYN project, the institutional repositories TMR and MR are also free of charge. For long term preservation, Zenodo has a lifelong retention period and hence there will not be any costs associated to this. During the course of the project, the consortium members will decide on how long the data will be stored in the repositories TMR and Zenodo.

4. DATA SECURITY

The data stored in the TMR is safe and protected. The TMR is managed by the TM responsible in Table 1. For accessing the data in TMR, user and password are requested. A periodic backup of the stored data is commonly performed.

The data stored in member repositories (MRs) are password protected and only those who are granted access are allowed to access the files. A periodic backup of the stored data is commonly performed.

Finally, all data in Zenodo repository are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas stored in different disks. The servers are managed according to CERN Security Baseline for Servers (<https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure>).

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

As it was stated in the GA, there are no ethical aspects that should be taken into consideration in the current project.

6. OTHER ISSUES

At the current moment, there are no other issues to be discussed. If foreseen during the course of the project, this section will be updated then.

ANNEX 1

WP 1: Dynamic modelling of material and structure (Leader: UdG)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D11_ModellingMethodology_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
	BEDYN_D12_SupportAnalysisToolsMethods_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf		
	BEDYN_D13_AnalysisExperimentalResults_UC3M_v1_date	Report	.pdf		
		Associated data: Spreadsheets (Excel; Matlab)	.xlsx; .m		
	BEDYN_D14_ValidationAndCalibrationModellingMethodology_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf		
		Associated data: Output databases (Abaqus) Fortran subroutines (for Abaqus) Input/Python models (Abaqus)	.odb .f .inp / .py		

WP 2: Test coupons/elements/structures design (Leader: UdG)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D21_DefinitionOfCoupons_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
		Associated data: Spreadsheets Excel (list of specimens and details)	.xlsx		
	BEDYN_D22_DefinitionOfElementsAndStructures_UC3M_v1_date	Report	.pdf		
		Associated data: Spreadsheets Excel (list of specimens and details)	.xlsx		

WP3: Test setup design (Leader: UC3M)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D31_DefinitionOfTestsForCoupons_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
		Associated data: Spreadsheets Excel (list of test setups and details)	.xlsx		
	BEDYN_D32_DefinitionOfTestsForElementsAndStructures_UC3M_v1_date	Report	.pdf		
		Associated data: Spreadsheets Excel (list of test setups and details)	.xlsx		

WP 4: Manufacturing: coupons, elements, structures and test rigs (Leader: COMPOXI)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D41_ManufacturedCouponsElementsAndStructures_COMPOXI_v1_date	Demonstrator	-	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
		Associated data: Reports of manufactured specimens with curing cycle, Non-Destructive Inspections, images of manufactured plates and cut specimens, dimension measurements, etc.	.pdf; .jpeg		
	BEDYN_D42_ManufacturedTestRigs_UC3M_v1_date	Demonstrator	-		
		Associated data: Cad files (AutoCad / SolidWorks)	.dwg; .sldprt		

WP 5: Quasi-static and dynamic tests (UC3M)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D51_TestReportCoupons_UC3M_v1_date	Report Associated data: In addition of the deliverable, additional info will be shared (reports, images and/or videos). It is worth noting that for some tests, a second dedicated report will be delivered with the following information: test details, results and incidents of each test, including individual specimen data and summary of the batch	.pdf .pdf; .jpeg; .mp4; .avi	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
	BEDYN_D53_TestReportElementsAndStructures_UC3M_v1_date	Report Associated data: In addition of the deliverable, additional info will be shared (reports, images and/or	.pdf .pdf; .jpeg; .mp4; .avi		

		videos). It is worth noting that for some tests, a second dedicated report will be delivered with the following information: test details, results and incidents of each test, including individual specimen data and summary of the batch			
	BEDYN_D52_TestDataCoupons_UC3M_v1_date	Data raw	.txt; .xlsx	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
	BEDYN_D54_TestDataElementsAndStructures_UC3M_v1_date	Data raw	.txt; .xlsx	Calculation Sheets developed before the BEDYN project, but used for its development, are not shared between partners either with external users	

WP 6: Project management (Leader: UdG)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D61_ImplementationAgreementConsortiumAgreement_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
	BEDYN_D62_DMPDataManagementPlan_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf Classified as "ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot"	TMR (Confidential) and Zenodo	TMR, MR and Zenodo
Project Management	Meeting Minutes + TM info (inputs) Reporting Period Meetings	Reports and presentations Reports and presentations	.pdf; .pptx .pdf; .pptx	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
	Timesheets and financial data (costs incurred for each consortium partner; annual salaries, social charges)	Spreadsheets	.xlsx (EC Guidelines)	The generated data will be shared only between the Coordinator, partner and the project officer	UdG's MR

WP 7: Dissemination and Communication (Leader: UdG)					
Category	Data Set Reference & Name	Data Set Description	Standards and Metadata	Data Sharing	Archiving and Preservation (including storage & backup)
Deliverables and linked data	BEDYN_D71_PEDR_PlanCommunicationDisseminationAndExploitationResults_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf	TMR (Confidential) and Zenodo	TMR, MR and Zenodo
	BEDYN_D72_SummaryDisseminationAndCommunicationActions_UdG_v1_date	Report	.pdf	TMR (Confidential) and Zenodo	TMR, MR and Zenodo
Other	Project visual identity (logo and templates)	Project logo Word template PowerPoint template	.pdf .docx .pptx	TMR (Confidential)	TMR and MR
	Publication of data classified as non-confidential (during and after the project)	News published on the website or social media, peer-reviewed papers, conference proceedings, technical notes	.pdf .docx .pptx internet	TMR (Confidential), Zenodo, webpages and networks	TMR, MR and Zenodo